

Determination of the inhibitory and pharmacokinetic properties of helipyrrone, norhelipyrrone, italipyrrone, bisnorhelipyrrone, and plicatipyrrone by *in silico* methods

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Figure S1. Bisnorhelipyrrone interaction with enzymes a): AChE, b): BChE, c): DPP-4, d): Monoamine Oxidase A, e): COX-2, f): stable-5-LOX, g): Tyrosinase, h): ACE-C-domain, i) ACE-N-domain

Figure S3. Helipyrrone interaction with enzymes **a):** AChE, **b):** BChE, **c):** DPP-4, **d):** Monoamine Oxidase A, **e):** COX-2, **f):** stable-5-LOX, **g):** Tyrosinase, **h):** ACE-C-domain, **i)** ACE-N-domain

Figure S4. Helipyrrone interaction with enzymes **a)** AChE, **b)** BChE, **c)** DPP-4, **d)** Monoamine Oxidase A, **e)** COX-2, **f)** stable-5-LOX, **g)** Tyrosinase, **h)** ACE-C-domain, **i)** ACE-N-domain

Figure S6. Norheliopyrone interaction with enzymes **a):** AChE, **b):** BChE, **c):** DPP-4, **d):** Monoamine Oxidase A, **e):** COX-2, **f):** stable-5-LOX, **g):** Tyrosinase, **h):** ACE-C-domain, **i)** ACE-N-domain

Figure S7. Norheligprone interaction with enzymes **a):** AChE, **b):** BChE, **c):** DPP-4, **d):** Monoamine Oxidase A, **e):** COX-2, **f):** stable-5-LOX, **g):** Tyrosinase, **h):** ACE-C-domain, **i):** ACE-N-domain

Figure S8. Plicatipyronne interaction with enzymes **a)**: AChE, **b)**: BChE, **c)**: DPP-4, **d)**: Monoamine Oxidase A, **e)**: COX-2, **f)**: stable-5-LOX, **g)**: Tyrosinase, **h)**: ACE-C-domain, **i)**: ACE-N-domain

Figure S10. Mulliken Charges views of Helipyrene and its derivatives

Figure S11. Molecular dynamics simulation of Plicatiprone with AChE and the MM/PBSA analysis results

Figure S12. Molecular dynamics simulation of Itaipyrone with AChE and the MM/PBSA analysis results

Tables

Table S1. 1C2O- helipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:ARG356:NH2 -	2,8880	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional	B:ARG356:NH2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O4	8		Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:O4	
2	P:POS1:H1 -	1,9720	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:GLU376:O	H-Acceptor
	B:GLU376:O	6		Hydrogen Bond			B:GLU376:O	
3	C:ARG534:CD -	3,3944	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen	C:ARG534:CD	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O5	8		Bond			P:POS1:O5	
4	B:LEU360:CD1 -	3,6668	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	B:LEU360:CD1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1						4,7596	
5	P:POS1:C12 -	4,7596	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	C:ARG534	Alkyl
	C:ARG534	3					C:ARG534	
6	P:POS1:C12 -	4,1521	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	C:LYS538	Alkyl
	C:LYS538	8					C:LYS538	
7	P:POS1:C13 -	3,8880	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
	B:LEU360	4					B:LEU360	
8	P:POS1:C14 -	3,8901	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LEU380	Alkyl
	B:LEU380	1					B:LEU380	
9	P:POS1:C15 -	5,1655	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
	B:LEU360	6					B:LEU360	
10	C:PHE535 -	5,2095	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C12	2					P:POS1:C	
11	C:PHE535 -	4,2363	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C14	1					P:POS1:C	
12	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	5,2523	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL379	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	4					B:VAL379	

Table S2. 1POI- helipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 -	1,87775	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU197:O	H-Acceptor
	A:GLU197:OE1			Hydrogen Bond			A:GLU197:OE1	
2	A:GLY439:CA -	3,74885	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen	A:GLY439:CA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O3			Bond			P:POS1:O3	
3	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	4,94544	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
4	A:PHE329 - P:POS1	5,67963	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:PHE329	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C13	3,66247	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
6	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C15	4,15394	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
7	P:POS1:C12 - A:LEU125	5,20403	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:LEU125	Alkyl
8	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C12	5,20271	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
9	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C12	4,84924	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
10	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C14	4,90769	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
11	A:TYR128 - P:POS1:C14	5,16279	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR128	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
12	A:PHE329 -	4,44566	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE329	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C15						P:POS1:C15	
13	A:TYR332 - P:POS1:C13	4,73969	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR332	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
14	A:TYR332 - P:POS1:C15	4,08056	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR332	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
15	A:TRP430 - P:POS1:C13	4,86699	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP430	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
16	A:TRP430 - P:POS1:C13	4,02659	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP430	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
17	P:POS1 - A:ALA328	4,03849	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:ALA328	Alkyl

Table S3. 2ONC- helipyronone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - B:PHE461:O	2,0501	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:PHE461:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H2 - A:THR468:OG1	1,8587	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:THR468:O G1	H-Acceptor
3	A:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O5	2,8274	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN598:HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:C12 - B:PRO475	4,8233	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
5	P:POS1:C13 - A:PRO475	3,9227	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
6	P:POS1:C15 - A:CYS474	1	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	A:CYS474	Alkyl
7	P:POS1:C15 - A:PRO475	4,7939	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
8	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	4,3241	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
9	A:TRP464 - A:TYR597	4,7918	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C12 - A:TYR597	5,0047	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C14 - A:TYR597	4,4207	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
12	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C13	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
13	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C15	4,3995	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
14	B:PHE461 - P:POS1:C14	4,2007	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
15	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	5,3910	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
16	P:POS1:C12 - B:TRP464	7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
17	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,7654	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
18	P:POS1:C12 - B:TRP464	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
19	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,8951	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
20	P:POS1:C14 - B:TRP464	8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
21	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	5,2338	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
22	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S4. 2Z5X- helipyronone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:GLY67:HN - P:POS1:O6	2,8187	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY67:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
2	A:CYS406:HG - P:POS1:O3	2,8532	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:CYS406:HG	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H1 - A:ARG51:O	2,7529	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:ARG51:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H1 - P:POS1:O6	2	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H2 - A:TYR407:O	2,5826	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:TYR407:O	H-Acceptor
6	A:GLY67:HA2 - P:POS1:O6	1,8017	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY67:HA2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
7	A:TYR444:C,O;MET445:N - P:POS1	1,6465	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:TYR444:C,O;MET445:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:ALA448 - P:POS1:C13	4,3412	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA448	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
9	A:ALA448 - P:POS1:C15	4,0850	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA448	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C13 - A:ILE23	1	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA448	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C13 - A:MET445	3,8537	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:ILE23	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C14 - A:LYS305	9	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:MET445	Alkyl
13	A:TYR69 - P:POS1:C12	5,1853	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:LYS305	Alkyl
14	A:PHE352 - P:POS1:C12	4,7614	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
15	A:PHE352 - P:POS1:C14	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
16	A:TYR407 - P:POS1:C12	4,9900	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR69	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
17	A:TYR407 - P:POS1:C14	5,0052	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE352	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
18	A:TYR407 - P:POS1:C12	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE352	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
19	A:TYR407 - P:POS1:C14	4,7761	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
20	P:POS1 - A:ARG51	5,1402	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
21	P:POS1 - A:MET445	9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
22	P:POS1 - A:MET445	4,6571	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:ARG51	Alkyl
23	P:POS1 - A:MET445	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:MET445	Alkyl
24	P:POS1 - A:MET445	5,1930	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:MET445	Alkyl
25	P:POS1 - A:MET445	5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:MET445	Alkyl

Table S5. 3LN1- helipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	C:THR547:HG1 - P:POS1:O1	2,81845	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:THR547:H G1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
2	C:SER549:HG - P:POS1:O2	1,58459	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:SER549:H G	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H1 - B:ASP254:OD1	2,23093	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:ASP254:O D1	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:O6 P:POS1:H2 -	2,91452	Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
5	B:GLN256:OE1 C:THR547:HB -	1,69544	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:GLN256:O E1	H-Acceptor
6	P:POS1:O5 C:SER552:HB1 -	2,32345	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	C:THR547:H B	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
7	P:POS1:O6 P:POS1:O6	2,75949	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	C:SER552:H B1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
8	C:SER549:HG - P:POS1 P:POS1:C13 -	2,27184	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	C:SER549:H G	H-Donor	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
9	B:LYS253	4,97727	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:LYS253	Alkyl

Table S6. 3V99- helipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:LYS441:HN - P:POS1:O6	2,27396	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS441:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 6	H-Acceptor
2	B:ARG438:HH12 - P:POS1:O5	2,79178	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG438:H H12	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 5	H-Acceptor
3	B:LYS441:HZ3 - P:POS1:O3	3,0848	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:LYS441:HZ 3	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 3	H-Acceptor
4	B:LYS441:HZ1 - P:POS1:O3	2,92895	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:LYS441:HZ 1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 3	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:O1 - B:ARG438:O	3,1809	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:O1	H-Donor	B:ARG438 :O	H-Acceptor
6	P:POS1:H21 - A:GLN437:O	2,73577	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H21	H-Donor	A:GLN437 :O	H-Acceptor
7	P:POS1:H22 - A:GLN437:O	1,92808	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H22	H-Donor	A:GLN437 :O	H-Acceptor
8	B:ARG438:HD2 - P:POS1:O5	2,87566	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG438:H D2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 5	H-Acceptor
9	B:LYS441:HE2 - P:POS1:O3	2,5078	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:LYS441:HE 2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 3	H-Acceptor
10	B:ARG438:NH2 - P:POS1	4,23713	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:ARG438:N H2	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
11	A:LYS441:HB2 - P:POS1	2,62349	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	A:LYS441:HB 2	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
12	A:ARG438 - P:POS1	5,133	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ARG438	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
13	A:LYS441 - P:POS1	4,76631	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:LYS441	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
14	B:ARG438 - P:POS1	4,36821	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ARG438	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
15	B:LYS441 - P:POS1	5,01486	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:LYS441	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
16	P:POS1:C1 - A:ARG520	4,80076	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	A:ARG520	Alkyl
17	P:POS1:C5 - A:MET440	4,87615	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C5	Alkyl	A:MET440	Alkyl
18	P:POS1:C5 - A:LYS441	5,01521	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C5	Alkyl	A:LYS441	Alkyl
19	P:POS1:C13 - B:ARG438	4,76189	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:ARG438	Alkyl
20	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	5,14335	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl

Table S7. 5M6B-helipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:ALA228:N - P:POS1:O6	2,7645	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ALA228:N	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 6	H-Acceptor
2	B:ASN229:ND2 - P:POS1:O2	3,1002 8	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ASN229:N D2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 2	H-Acceptor
3	B:TYR297:OH - P:POS1:O5	3,1877	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:TYR297:O H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 5	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H1 - P:POS1:O4	1,9910 8	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 4	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H2 - A:ASP240:O	2,4859	Bond	Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:ASP240: O	H-Acceptor
6	B:HIS243:CE1 - P:POS1:O3	3,6094 4	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:HIS243:C E1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 3	H-Acceptor
7	A:ASP241:OD1 - P:POS1	4,8100 1	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	A:ASP241:O D1	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	P:POS1:C14 - B:LEU540	5,4237 6	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LEU540 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
9	B:PHE226 - P:POS1:C12	3,8987 6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE226	Pi-Orbitals	12 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
10	B:PHE239 - P:POS1:C13	5,1866 7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE239	Pi-Orbitals	13 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
11	B:HIS243 - P:POS1:C12	4,8311 2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS243	Pi-Orbitals	12 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
12	B:HIS243 - P:POS1:C14 B:PHE537 -	5,1343 8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS243	Pi-Orbitals	14 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
13	P:POS1:C12	5,2948 4,6358	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE537	Pi-Orbitals	12	Alkyl
14	P:POS1 - B:ALA228	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ALA228	Alkyl

Table S8. 6H5W-helipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:HIS353:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,2596 6	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS353:H E2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
2	A:HIS513:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,0775 3	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS513:H E2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	A:TYR523:HH - P:POS1:O3	2,7412	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR523:H H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLU411:OE1	2,5120 1	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU411:O E1	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS383:NE2	2,0189 2	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS383:N E2	H-Acceptor
6	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS387:NE2	3,0737 9	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS387:N E2	H-Acceptor
7	A:GLU411:OE1 - P:POS1	4,5018 5,8883	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	A:GLU411:O E1	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:TYR523 - P:POS1 P:POS1:C13 -	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
9	A:VAL518	4,5026 4,2284	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:VAL518	Alkyl
10	A:HIS383 - P:POS1:C14	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS383	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
11	A:HIS387 - P:POS1:C15 A:PHE457 -	3,7829 4,5187	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS387	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C12 A:TYR523 -	3 4,6951	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE457	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
13	P:POS1:C12 A:TYR523 -	5 4,0898	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
14	P:POS1:C14	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl

Table S9. 6H5X-helipyronone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - A:PHE461:O	1,68227	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:PHE461:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H2 - B:THR468:OG1	2,15208	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:THR468:OG1	H-Acceptor
3	B:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O5	2,53755	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN598:HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
4	B:TRP464:C,O;TYR465:N - P:POS1	4,03325	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	B:TRP464:C,O;TYR465:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	P:POS1:C12 - A:PRO475	4,3887	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
6	P:POS1:C15 - B:PRO475	4,39028	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
7	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	4,7397	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
8	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,38159	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
9	A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C13	4,70072	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
10	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	4,84832	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
11	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	4,08552	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
12	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C15	5,16438	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
13	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	5,40008	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
14	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C15	5,29641	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
15	B:TYR597 - P:POS1:C14	4,45843	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
16	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C15	4,60764	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl

Table S10. 1C2O-bisnorhelipyronone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:ARG356:NE - P:POS1:O6	3,1067	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG356:NE	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
2	B:ARG356:NH2 - P:POS1:O6	2,9191	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG356:NH2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	B:LEU380:N - P:POS1:O3	2,8017	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:LEU380:N	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H1 - B:GLU376:O	2,0231	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:GLU376:O	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H2 - B:GLU376:OE2	2,1487	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:GLU376:OE2	H-Acceptor
6	B:LEU360:CD1 - P:POS1	3,5364	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	B:LEU360:CD1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	P:POS1:C12 - C:ARG534	4,7544	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	C:ARG534	Alkyl
8	P:POS1:C12 - C:LYS538	4,1234	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	C:LYS538	Alkyl
9	P:POS1:C13 - B:LEU360	3,7941	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C14 - B:LEU380	3,7094	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LEU380	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C15 - B:LEU360	4,3373	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
12	C:PHE535 - P:POS1:C12	5,1355	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
13	C:PHE535 - P:POS1:C14	4,3159	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
14	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	5,0785	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL379	Alkyl

Table S11. 1POI-bisnorheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLU197:OE1	2,14576	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU197:O E1	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS438:O	2,05703	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS438:O	H-Acceptor
3	A:ALA328:CB - P:POS1	3,82594	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	A:ALA328: CB	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
4	A:PHE329 - P:POS1	5,61206	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:PHE329	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C13	3,5459	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
6	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C15	4,37774	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
7	A:LEU125 P:POS1:C12 -	5,4582	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1 2	Alkyl	A:LEU125	Alkyl
8	A:MET437 P:POS1:C15 -	4,69193	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1 5	Alkyl	A:MET437	Alkyl
9	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C12	5,16751	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
10	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C15	4,49643	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
11	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C12	4,85331	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
12	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C14	4,74473	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
13	A:TYR128 - P:POS1:C14	5,36236	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR128	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
14	A:TYR332 - P:POS1:C13	4,63738	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR332	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
15	A:TRP430 - P:POS1:C13	4,84252	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP430	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
16	A:TRP430 - P:POS1:C15	3,97494	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP430	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
17	A:TRP430 - P:POS1:C13	3,93524	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP430	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
18	A:TRP430 - P:POS1:C15	4,45442	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP430	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
19	A:TYR440 - P:POS1:C15	4,59574	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR440	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl

Table S12. 2ONC-bisnorheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - A:PHE461:O	2,13926	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:PHE461:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H2 - B:THR468:OG1	1,77831	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:THR468:O G1	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:C12 - A:PRO475	4,86031	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
4	P:POS1:C13 - B:PRO475	4,55496	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
5	P:POS1:C15 - B:PRO475	4,07377	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
6	A:PHE461 - P:POS1:C14	5,43318	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
7	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	5,08579	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
8	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,89793	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
9	A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C13	4,64448	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
10	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	5,0359	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
11	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	4,27879	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
12	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C15	4,8658	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
13	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	5,48736	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
14	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C15	4,9505	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
15	B:TYR597 - P:POS1:C12	4,93782	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
16	B:TYR597 - P:POS1:C14	4,34536	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
17	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C15	4,64242	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl

Table S13. 2Z5X-bisnorheliglypyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:GLY67:HN - P:POS1:O5	2,2373	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY67:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
2	A:CYS406:HG - P:POS1:O6	2,6530	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:CYS406:HG	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H1 - A:TYR407:O	1,7305	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:TYR407:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H2 - A:GLY443:O	2,1836	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:GLY443:O	H-Acceptor
5	A:GLY67:HA2 - P:POS1:O5	2,3932	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY67:HA2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
6	A:CYS406:SG - P:POS1	5,3764	Other	Pi-Sulfur	A:CYS406:SG	Sulfur	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	A:GLY66:C,O;GLY67:N - P:POS1	4,3315	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:GLY66:C,O;GLY67:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:ALA448 - P:POS1:C12	3,6164	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA448	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
9	A:ALA448 - P:POS1:C14	4,1318	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA448	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C12 - A:ILE23	3,8154	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:ILE23	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C12 - A:MET445	4,5831	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:MET445	Alkyl
12	A:TYR69 - P:POS1:C13	5,2610	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR69	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
13	A:PHE352 - P:POS1:C13	4,9077	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE352	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
14	A:TYR407 - P:POS1:C13	4,9744	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
15	A:TYR444 - P:POS1:C15	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR444	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
5	A:TYR444 - P:POS1:C15	5,0231	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR444	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl

Table S14. 3LN1-bisnorheliglypyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:GLN256:HE22 - P:POS1:O5	2,39604	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN256:HE22	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
2	C:SER549:HG - P:POS1:H1	1,8311	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:SER549:HG	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	C:THR547:O - P:POS1:H2	2,00554	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	C:THR547:O	H-Acceptor
4	B:GLN256:OE1 - C:SER552:HB1	1,6344	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:GLN256:OE1	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:O2	2,27436	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	C:SER552:HB1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor

Table S15. 3V99-bisnorheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:LYS441:HN - P:POS1:O5 B:ARG438:HH12 - P:POS1:O6	2,61724	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS441:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:O6	2,38153	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG438:HH12	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H1 - B:ARG438:O B:GLN437:C,O;ARG438:N - P:POS1	2,37202	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:ARG438:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1	4,81542	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	B:GLN437:C,O;ARG438:N	Amide	P:POS1 B:ARG438	Pi-Orbitals
5	P:POS1:C13 - B:ARG438	4,81597	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	8	Alkyl
6	P:POS1:C14 - A:LYS441	4,56259	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	A:LYS441	Alkyl
7	P:POS1:C14 - B:LYS441	3,89553	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LYS441	Alkyl
8	P:POS1:C15 - A:ARG438	4,32074	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	A:ARG438	Alkyl
9	P:POS1 - A:ARG438	4,5157	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	8	Alkyl
10	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	3,89786	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl

Table S16. 5M6B-bisnorheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
B:ARG367:NH1 - P:POS1:O3	3,09446	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG367:NH1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
B:ARG367:NH1 - P:POS1:O6	2,94985	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG367:NH1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
P:POS1:H1 - B:LEU296:O	1,71552	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:LEU296:O	H-Acceptor
P:POS1:H2 - B:LEU296:O	2,64695	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:LEU296:O	H-Acceptor
B:ARG367:CD - P:POS1:O3	3,00172	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG367:CD	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
B:ARG367:CD - P:POS1	3,5275	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	B:ARG367:CD	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
B:TYR297 - P:POS1	5,99592	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:TYR297	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
P:POS1:C12 - B:VAL300	4,38438	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	B:VAL300	Alkyl
P:POS1:C13 - B:ARG367	3,99851	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:ARG367	Alkyl
P:POS1:C14 - B:PRO298	3,4498	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:PRO298	Alkyl
P:POS1:C15 - B:LEU296	3,51112	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:LEU296	Alkyl
P:POS1:C15 - B:ARG367	5,03342	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:ARG367	Alkyl
B:TYR297 - P:POS1:C12	5,22742	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR297	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
B:PHE537 - P:POS1:C15	5,46138	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE537	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
P:POS1 - B:ARG367	4,8717	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG367	Alkyl

Table S17. 6H5W-bisnorheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:HIS353:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,31294	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS353:HE2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
2	A:HIS513:HE2 - P:POS1:O5	2,49077	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS513:HE2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
3	A:HIS513:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,3008	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS513:HE2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLU384:OE2	1,79039	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU384:OE2	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS383:NE2	2,14865	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS383:NE2	H-Acceptor
6	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS387:NE2	3,09491	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS387:NE2	H-Acceptor
7	A:HIS353:HD2 - P:POS1:O6	2,94365	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS353:HD2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
8	A:GLU411:OE1 - P:POS1	4,53416	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	A:GLU411:OE1	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
9	A:TYR523 - P:POS1	5,90543	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
10	P:POS1:C13 - A:VAL518	4,4318	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:VAL518	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C14 - A:VAL380	3,45678	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	A:VAL380	Alkyl
12	A:HIS383 - P:POS1:C12	4,08083	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS383	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
13	A:HIS383 - P:POS1:C14	4,26078	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS383	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
14	A:HIS387 - P:POS1:C15	3,65573	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS387	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
15	A:TYR523 - P:POS1:C12	5,39937	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S18. 6H5X-bisnorheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
P:POS1:H1 - A:THR468:OG1	1,73598	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:THR468:OG1	H-Acceptor
P:POS1:H2 - A:TYR597:O	2,3269	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:TYR597:O	H-Acceptor
B:TYR465:HA - P:POS1:O2	3,08092	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:TYR465:HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
P:POS1:H6 - A:TRP464:O	2,45784	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H6	H-Donor	A:TRP464:O	H-Acceptor
P:POS1:H6 - A:THR468:OG1	2,27641	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H6	H-Donor	A:THR468:OG1	H-Acceptor
B:PHE461 - P:POS1	4,89548	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
P:POS1:C12 - A:PRO475	3,88367	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
P:POS1:C14 - A:CYS474	4,8953	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	A:CYS474	Alkyl
A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	4,10947	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,47791	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	5,24902	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,35098	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C13	5,49314	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C15	4,23744	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	5,17031	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C14	4,73588	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	5,00099	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
B:TYR597 - P:POS1:C12	5,04686	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S19. 1C2O-Italipyronone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H3 - B:GLU376:O	2,1335 4	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H3 B:GLU376:C	H-Donor	B:GLU376 :O	H-Acceptor
2	B:GLU376:CA - P:POS1:O3	2,9440 7	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A	H-Donor	3	H-Acceptor
3	B:GLU376:OE2 - P:POS1	4,2327 6	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	B:GLU376:O E2	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
4	B:GLU376:OE2 - P:POS1	3,7938 3	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	B:GLU376:O E2	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	B:LEU360:CD1 - P:POS1	3,4967 9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	B:LEU360:C D1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
6	B:LEU360 - P:POS1 P:POS1:C19 -	3,6265 5,1125	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
7	C:ARG534 P:POS1:C19 -	1	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl	C:ARG534	Alkyl
8	C:LYS538 P:POS1:C21 -	4,1101 3,7664	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl	C:LYS538	Alkyl
9	B:LEU380 C:PHE535 -	6	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	B:LEU380 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C19 C:PHE535 -	4,7628	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	19 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C21	4,2589 4,2365	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	21	Alkyl
12	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL379	Alkyl

Table S20. 1POI-Italipyronone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR128:OH - P:POS1:O6	2,61271	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR128:OH	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 6	H- Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H1 - A:TRP82:O	1,67033	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	O	H- Acceptor
3	A:TYR128:OH A:THR120:OG1 -	2,19143	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:TYR128: OH	H- Acceptor
4	P:POS1	4,09674	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	A:THR120:OG1	H-Donor	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	P:POS1:O7 - A:TRP82	2,98361	Other	Pi-Lone Pair	P:POS1:O7	Lone Pair Pi- Orbitals	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals
6	A:HIS438 - P:POS1 A:GLY115:C,O;GLY116:	4,52377	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:HIS438 A:GLY115:C,O;	Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	N - P:POS1	4,12812	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	GLY116:N	Amide	P:POS1 P:POS1:C	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C19	3,32373	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	19 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
9	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C21 P:POS1:C19 -	3,51046	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	21	Alkyl
10	A:MET437	4,87425	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl Pi- Orbitals	A:MET437 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
11	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C19 A:PHE329 -	5,10969	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi- Orbitals	19 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C21	3,91982	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE329	Pi- Orbitals	21 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
13	A:HIS438 - P:POS1:C21	5,25876	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS438	Pi- Orbitals	21 P:POS1:C	Alkyl
14	A:TYR440 - P:POS1:C19	5,34893	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR440	Pi- Orbitals	19	Alkyl
15	P:POS1 - A:ALA328	5,35144	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi- Orbitals	A:ALA328	Alkyl

Table S21. 2ONC-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - B:THR468:OG1	1,7250 3	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:THR468:O G1	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H3 - A:TYR597:O	2,2213 7	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	A:TYR597:O	H-Acceptor
3	A:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O5	2,8193 5	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN598:H A	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
4	B:TYR465:HA - P:POS1:O2	3,0541 5	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:TYR465:H A	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
5	B:PRO475:HD1 - P:POS1:O6	2,2824 5	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:PRO475:H D1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
6	B:PRO475:HD2 - P:POS1:O6	2,3673 9	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:PRO475:H D2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
7	B:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O7	2,7398 2	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN598:H A	H-Donor	P:POS1:O7	H-Acceptor
8	A:HIS600 - P:POS1 P:POS1:C19 -	4,5308 7 3,8614	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
9	A:PRO475 P:POS1:C21 -	8 4,7163	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
10	A:CYS474 P:POS1:C21 -	7 4,6778	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	A:CYS474	Alkyl
11	A:PRO475 A:PHE461 -	7 3,9019	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C12 A:TRP464 -	8 4,0209	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
13	P:POS1:C19 A:TRP464 -	7 4,8582	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl
14	P:POS1:C19 A:TYR465 -	3 4,6776	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl
15	P:POS1:C12 A:TYR465 -	5 4,7273	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
16	P:POS1:C17 A:TYR465 -	4 5,1048	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
17	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C19 A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C21	2 4,1904 9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl
18	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C21 B:PHE461 -	9 4,4544	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl
19	P:POS1:C17 B:PHE461 -	7 4,2849	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
20	B:TYR465 - P:POS1:C12	1 1	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S22. 2Z5X-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:ARG51:HH12 - P:POS1:O7	2,3261 2,4430	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG51:HH12	H-Donor	P:POS1: O7	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLY66:O	4 2,5202	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLY66: O	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H16 - A:TRP397	2 5,0523	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	P:POS1:H16	C-H	A:TRP39 7	Pi-Orbitals
4	A:CYS406:SG - P:POS1	3 5,9707	Other	Pi-Sulfur	A:CYS406:SG	Sulfur	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	A:MET445:SD - P:POS1 A:GLY66:C,O;GLY67:N - P:POS1	9 4,1655 4	Other Hydrophobic	Pi-Sulfur	A:MET445:SD	Sulfur	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
6	P:POS1	4	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:GLY66:C,O;GL Y67:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	P:POS1:C19 - A:ARG51	4,0278 4,8208	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl	A:ARG51	Alkyl
8	P:POS1:C21 - A:ILE23	4 3,9407	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	A:ILE23 A:MET44	Alkyl
9	P:POS1:C21 - A:MET445	1	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	5 P:POS1:	Alkyl
10	A:TYR69 - P:POS1:C12	5,4973	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR69	Pi-Orbitals	C12	Alkyl
11	A:TYR407 - P:POS1	4,8488 4,6531	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1 P:POS1:	Alkyl
12	A:TYR444 - P:POS1:C12	3 4,4190	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR444	Pi-Orbitals	C12 P:POS1:	Alkyl
13	A:TYR444 - P:POS1:C17	3 4,1209	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR444	Pi-Orbitals	C17	Alkyl
14	P:POS1 - A:ARG51	1	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:ARG51	Alkyl

Table S23. 3LN1-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:LYS239:HZ3 -	2,3389	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	B:LYS239:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O7	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O7	6	Bond	Bond	Z3			
2	C:SER549:HG -	1,8757	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	C:SER549:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O6	7	Bond	Bond	G			
3	C:SER552:HG -	2,6277	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	C:SER552:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O2	9	Bond	Bond	G			
4	P:POS1:H1 -	1,6605	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	C:THR547:O	H-Acceptor
	C:THR547:O	5	Bond	Bond				
5	P:POS1:H2 -	1,6711	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:ASP254:O	H-Acceptor
	B:ASP254:O	8	Bond	Bond				
6	P:POS1:H3 -	2,3453	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	B:THR255:O	H-Acceptor
	B:THR255:O	4	Bond	Bond				
7	P:POS1:H3 -	2,6295	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	B:GLN256:O	H-Acceptor
	B:GLN256:OE1	5	Bond	Bond				
8	P:POS1:H3 -	3,0259	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O3	7	Bond	Bond				
9	B:LYS239:HE1 -	3,0945	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	B:LYS239:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O7	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O7	1	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	E1			
10	C:SER552:HB1 -	2,4635	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	C:SER552:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O2	2	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B1			
11	P:POS1:C19 -	4,1053	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl	B:LYS229	Alkyl
	B:LYS229	8						
12	P:POS1:C21 -	3,9771	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	B:LYS229	Alkyl
	B:LYS229							
13	P:POS1 - B:LYS229	3,9029	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS229	Alkyl

Table S24. 3V99-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 -	2,2779	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:GLY291:O	H-Acceptor
	B:GLY291:O	3	Bond	Bond				
2	P:POS1:H2 -	2,5190	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O7	9	Bond	Bond				
3	P:POS1:H3 -	2,1467	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	A:GLN437:O	H-Acceptor
	A:GLN437:O	6	Bond	Bond				
4	P:POS1:H3 -	2,0761	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O1	6	Bond	Bond				
5	B:ARG438:HA -	2,3550	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	B:ARG438:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O7	3	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A			
6	P:POS1:H4 -	2,6005	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H4	H-Donor	A:GLY150:O	H-Acceptor
	A:GLY150:O	7	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond				
7	B:ARG438:NH1 -	3,6334	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:ARG438:N	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1	4,6298			H1			
8	B:ARG438:NH2 -	4,6298	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:ARG438:N	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1	2			H2			
9	A:GLN437:HB1 -	2,2668	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	A:GLN437:H	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1	6			B1			
10	A:LYS441:HB2 -	2,7832	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	A:LYS441:H	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1	1			B2			
11	P:POS1:C17 -	3,9600	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl	A:MET440	Alkyl
	A:MET440	4						
12	P:POS1:C19 -	4,3432	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl	A:LYS441	Alkyl
	A:LYS441	4						
13	P:POS1:C21 -	4,0494	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	A:LYS441	Alkyl
	A:LYS441	3						
14	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	4,6692	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl
		7						
15	P:POS1 - B:LYS441	5,2360	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS441	Alkyl
		3						
16	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	4,8722	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl
		1						

Table S25. 5M6B-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H2 - B:LEU296:O	1,3816	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:LEU296:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H3 - B:PRO298:O	2,1660	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:H3	
3	B:ARG367:NH1 - P:POS1	3,3553	Electrostatic Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Cation	B:ARG367:NH1	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	A:THR303:OG1 - P:POS1	3,8611						
4	P:POS1	5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	G1	H-Donor	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	B:TYR297 - P:POS1	5,1732						
6	B:ALA228 - P:POS1:C19	3,9654	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ALA228	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C12 - A:PRO306	3,7627					P:POS1:C12	
8	P:POS1:C17 - A:PRO306	4,4001	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl	A:PRO306	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C19 - B:VAL300	5,0423					P:POS1:C19	
9	B:TYR297 - P:POS1:C21	5,1181	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR297	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL300	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C21	1					P:POS1:C21	

Table S26. 6H5W-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR394:HH - P:POS1:O6	2,5518	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR394:HH	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	A:ARG522:HH12 - P:POS1:O7	2,4332	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			A:ARG522:H12	
3	P:POS1:H1 - A:ARG402:O	2,0048	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:ARG402:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 - P:POS1:O5	1,8381	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:H2	
5	A:GLU411:OE2 - P:POS1	3,3781	Electrostatic Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Anion Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	A:GLU411:OE2	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1:H3 - A:HIS387	2,1196						
7	A:HIS387 - P:POS1	4,8915	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	A:HIS387	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	A:HIS410 - P:POS1	4,0751						
9	P:POS1:C12 - A:MET223	4,8371	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:MET223	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C12 - A:PRO407	3,6550						
11	P:POS1:C17 - A:PRO407	3,8777	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl	A:PRO407	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C19 - A:VAL518	4,2644						
13	A:HIS387 - P:POS1:C21	4,6514	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS387	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C	Alkyl
	A:HIS410 - P:POS1	4,6982					A:HIS410	
15	A:HIS410 - P:POS1:C17	4,6956	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS410	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C	Alkyl
	A:HIS410 - P:POS1:C17	7					A:HIS410	

Table S27. 6H5X-Italipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - A:THR468:OG1	1,854	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:THR468:O G1	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H3 - B:TYR597:O	1,6941 3	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	B:TYR597:O	H-Acceptor
3	A:TYR465:HA - P:POS1:O2	2,6432 4	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR465: HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
4	A:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O7	2,8317 6	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN598: HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O7	H-Acceptor
5	B:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O5	2,2945 4	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN598: HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
6	B:His600 - P:POS1 P:POS1:C19 -	4,3902 3,8456	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:His600 P:POS1:C1 9	Pi-Orbitals Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals Alkyl
7	B:PRO475 P:POS1:C21 -	5 4,5423	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C2 1	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
8	B:CYS474 P:POS1:C21 -	8 5,3129	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C2 1	Alkyl	B:CYS474	Alkyl
9	B:PRO475	7	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	1	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
10	A:PHE461 - P:POS1 A:PHE461 -	5,4249 4,5086	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C17 A:TYR465 -	8 4,6522	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C12 B:PHE461 -	2 3,9899	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
13	P:POS1:C12 B:TRP464 -	9 4,5761	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
14	P:POS1:C19 B:TRP464 -	2 5,0313	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl
15	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C19	4 4,8849	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl
16	B:TYR465 - P:POS1:C12	4,9830 2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
17	B:TYR465 - P:POS1:C17	4,9830 6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
18	B:His600 - P:POS1:C19 B:His600 - P:POS1:C21	4,4834 6 4,0086	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:His600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C19	Alkyl
19	B:His600 - P:POS1:C21	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:His600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl

Table S28. 1C2O-norheliopyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:ARG356:NE - P:POS1:O6	3,0660 6	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG356:N E	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
2	B:ARG356:NH2 - P:POS1:O6	2,9404 4	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG356:N H2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H1 - B:GLU376:O	2,0406 5	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:GLU376:O B:GLU376:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H2 - B:GLU376:OE2	Hydrogen 2,2264	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	E2	H-Acceptor
5	C:ARG534:CD - P:POS1:O5	3,7774 9	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	C:ARG534:C D	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
6	B:LEU360:CD1 - P:POS1	3,5316 8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	B:LEU360:C D1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	P:POS1:C12 - C:ARG534	4,6101 4	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	C:ARG534	Alkyl
8	P:POS1:C12 - C:LYS538	4,1865 9	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	C:LYS538	Alkyl
9	P:POS1:C13 - B:LEU360	3,8624 9	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C14 - B:LEU380	3,8788 3	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LEU380	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C15 - B:LEU360	4,2351 4,3500	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
12	C:PHE535 - P:POS1:C12	5,3500 6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
13	C:PHE535 - P:POS1:C14	4,3698 9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	C:PHE535	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
14	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	5,1937 8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL379	Alkyl

Table S29. 1POI-norheligyprone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR128:OH - P:POS1:O2	2,6011	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR128:OH	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
2	A:GLY439:CA - P:POS1:O5	3,2963	Hydrogen Bond	Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY439:CA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
3	A:GLY115:C,O;GLY116:N - P:POS1	3,7843	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:GLY115:C,O;GLY116:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
4	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C12	3,7359	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
5	A:ALA328 - P:POS1:C14	3,1503	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA328	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
6	P:POS1:C12 - A:MET437	4,8387	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	A:MET437	Alkyl
7	P:POS1:C13 - A:LEU125	4,2342	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:LEU125	Alkyl
8	A:TRP82 - P:POS1:C12	4,7181	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
9	A:PHE329 - P:POS1:C14	3,9358	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE329	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
10	A:HIS438 - P:POS1:C14	4,9097	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS438	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
11	A:TYR440 - P:POS1:C12	4,9373	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR440	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S30. 2ONC-norheligyprone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - B:PHE461:O	2,0768	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:PHE461:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H6 - P:POS1:O4	1,4868	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H6	H-Donor	P:POS1:O4	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:C12 - B:CYS474	5,2801	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	B:CYS474	Alkyl
4	P:POS1:C12 - B:PRO475	4,3316	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
5	P:POS1:C14 - B:PRO475	4,8993	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
6	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	5,3939	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
7	A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C14	4,6991	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
8	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C15	5,2363	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
9	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,6027	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
10	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	5,2329	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
11	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	4,5859	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S31. 2Z5X-norheligprone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:ALA68:HN -	2,3698	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	A:ALA68:	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O3	2	Bond	Bond	HN			
2	P:POS1:H1 -	2,3328	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H	H-Donor	A:TYR69:O	H-Acceptor
	A:TYR69:O	2	Bond	Bond	1			
3	P:POS1:H2 -	1,8329	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H	H-Donor	A:GLN215:O	H-Acceptor
	A:GLN215:OE1	8	Bond	Bond	2			
4	P:POS1:C13 - A:ILE180	4,5746	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C	Alkyl	A:ILE180	Alkyl
		3			13			
5	P:POS1:C13 - A:ILE335	4,5392	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C	Alkyl	A:ILE335	Alkyl
		6			13			
6	P:POS1:C14 - A:MET445	3,2945	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C	Alkyl	A:MET445	Alkyl
		8			14			
7	P:POS1:C15 - A:ILE180	5,0503	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C	Alkyl	A:ILE180	Alkyl
		9			15			
8	A:PHE352 -	4,4896	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE352	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C13	5						
9	A:TYR407 -	5,4297	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C12	5						
10	A:TYR407 -	5,4683	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C13	1						

Table S32. 3LN1-norheligprone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	D:LYS123:HN -	1,9137	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	D:LYS123:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O5	3	Bond	Bond	N			
2	D:LYS123:HZ1 -	2,8051	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	D:LYS123:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O5	2,1969	Bond	Bond	Z1			
3	C:SER534:O	2	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	C:SER534:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 -	2,1359	Hydrogen	Conventional Hydrogen	P:POS1:H2			
4	D:TYR116:OH	5	Bond	Bond	C:THR535:HA	H-Donor	D:TYR116:OH	H-Acceptor
	C:THR535:HA -	2,3279	Hydrogen	Bond	HA			
5	P:POS1:O1	5	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	D:TYR122:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
	D:TYR122:HA -	2,2091	Hydrogen	Bond	A			
6	P:POS1:O5	1	Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	D:TYR122:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
	D:CYS32:O - P:POS1	2,7114	Other	Pi-Lone Pair	A			
7	P:POS1:C12 -	4,8230	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	D:CYS32:O	Lone Pair	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	C:LEU320	2			P:POS1:C1			
8	P:POS1:C12 -	5,1868	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	C:LEU320	Alkyl
	D:LYS123	6			2			
9	P:POS1:C15 -	4,3554	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl	D:LYS123	Alkyl
	D:PRO139	1			5			
10	C:TRP309 -	4,2348	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	D:PRO139	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C14	9			C:TRP309			
11	D:TYR116 -	4,8372	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	D:TYR116	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C15	2			5			
12	D:TYR122 -	4,9529	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	D:TYR122	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C12	8			2			
13	D:TYR122 -	4,2491	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	D:TYR122	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C1	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C14	7			4			

Table S33. 3V99-norheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:LYS441:HN - P:POS1:O5	2,3949	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:LYS441:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
	B:ARG438:HH12 - P:POS1:O4	2,8554	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			B:ARG438:H12	
2	B:LYS441:HZ1 - P:POS1:O6	2,8318	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:LYS441:HZ1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H1 - B:ARG438:O	2,3079	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:H1	
3	P:POS1:H2 - A:GLN437:O	2,1784	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:GLN437:O	H-Acceptor
	B:LYS441:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,5465	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			B:LYS441:HE2	
4	P:POS1:C13 - B:ARG438	4,9629	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	B:ARG438	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C14 - A:LYS441	4,5042					A:LYS441	
5	P:POS1:C14 - B:LYS441	3,9426	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LYS441	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - A:ARG438	4,3563					P:POS1	
6	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	4,0157	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	9					Pi-Alkyl	

Table S34. 5MB6-norheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:ASN229:ND2 - P:POS1:O5	2,5898	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ASN229:ND2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
	B:ASN229:ND2 - P:POS1:O4	2,6671	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			B:ASN229:ND2	
2	P:POS1:H1 - B:ASP241:OD1	1,6758	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:ASP241:OD1	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 - B:ASP241:O	2,8592	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:H2	
3	P:POS1:H6 - B:ASP240:OD1	2,7787	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H6	H-Donor	B:ASP240:OD1	H-Acceptor
	A:ALA228 - P:POS1:C12	4,2599	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			A:ALA228	
4	A:ALA228 - P:POS1:C14	4,4338			Hydrophobic	Alkyl		A:ALA228
	A:HIS243 - P:POS1:C12	4,3135	A:HIS243	Pi-Orbitals			P:POS1:C12	
5	A:HIS243 - P:POS1:C14	4,4852	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS243	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
	B:HIS243 - P:POS1:C13	4,4347					B:HIS243	
6	B:HIS243 - P:POS1:C15	4,4234	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS243	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
	B:HIS243 - P:POS1:C15	9					Pi-Alkyl	

Table S35. 6H5W-norheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:HIS353:HE2 - P:POS1:O5	2,9249	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS353:H E2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
2	A:HIS353:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,3295	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS353:H E2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
3	A:HIS513:HE2 - P:POS1:O5	2,4450	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS513:H E2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
4	A:HIS513:HE2 - P:POS1:O6	2,2678	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS513:H E2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLU384:OE2	1,8205	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU384:O E2	H-Acceptor
6	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS383:NE2	2,1381	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS383:N E2	H-Acceptor
7	P:POS1:H2 - A:HIS387:NE2	3,0381	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:HIS387:N E2	H-Acceptor
8	A:HIS353:HD2 - P:POS1:O6	2,9994	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS353:H D2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
9	A:GLU411:OE1 - P:POS1	4,5050	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	A:GLU411:O E1	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
10	A:TYR523 - P:POS1	5,9146	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
11	P:POS1:C13 - A:VAL518	4,4392	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:VAL518	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C14 - A:VAL380	3,7225	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	A:VAL380	Alkyl
13	A:HIS383 - P:POS1:C12	4,2510	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS383	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
14	A:HIS383 - P:POS1:C14	4,0556	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS383	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
15	A:HIS387 - P:POS1:C15	3,6735	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS387	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
16	A:TYR523 - P:POS1:C12	5,1682	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
17	A:PHE527 - P:POS1:C12	4	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
		5,4286	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE527	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
		5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE527	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S36. 6H5X-norheliopyrone interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - B:PHE461:O	2,12579	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:PHE461:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H2 - A:THR468:OG1	1,87645	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:THR468:OG1	H-Acceptor
3	A:GLN598:HA - P:POS1:O5	2,7979	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN598:HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
4	A:TRP464:C,O;TYR465:N - P:POS1	4,37199	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:TRP464:C,O;TYR465:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
5	P:POS1:C12 - B:PRO475	4,78073	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
6	P:POS1:C13 - A:PRO475	4,47133	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
7	P:POS1:C15 - A:PRO475	4,05262	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl	A:PRO475	Alkyl
8	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C13	4,27784	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
9	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C15	4,9218	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
10	A:TRP464 - P:POS1:C15	5,0763	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
11	A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C12	5,12555	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
12	A:TYR597 - P:POS1:C14	4,41031	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
13	A:HIS600 - P:POS1:C15	4,64771	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C15	Alkyl
14	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C12	5,06505	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl
15	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C14	4,75157	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
16	B:TYR597 - P:POS1:C13	4,66022	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
17	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C12	4,8777	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C12	Alkyl

Table S37. 1C2O-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:ARG356:NH2 - P:POS1:O4	3,1013	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG356:NH2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H1 - C:ARG534:O	2,8521	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:H1	
2	C:ARG534:O - P:POS1:H2	9	Bond	Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:GLU376:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 - B:GLU376:O	2,2509	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond			P:POS1:H2	
3	B:GLU376:O - B:GLU376:CA	5	Bond	Bond	B:GLU376:CA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
	B:GLU376:CA - P:POS1:O6	3,7598	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			B:GLU376:CA	
4	B:GLU376:OE2 - P:POS1	4,7677	Bond	Bond	B:GLU376:OE2	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1 - B:LEU360:CD1	8	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion			B:GLU376:OE2	
5	B:LEU360:CD1 - P:POS1	3,4282	Bond	Bond	B:LEU360:CD1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1 - B:TRP385	7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma			B:LEU360:CD1	
6	B:TRP385 - P:POS1	5,4152	Bond	Bond	B:TRP385	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1 - C:ARG534	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped			B:TRP385	
7	C:ARG534 - P:POS1	5,2615	Bond	Bond	C:ARG534	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - B:LEU360	3,8864	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			C:ARG534	
8	P:POS1:C14 - B:LEU360	1	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LEU360	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C16 - B:LEU360	3,8206	Hydrophobic	Alkyl			P:POS1:C16	
9	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	4,6296	Bond	Bond	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL379	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - C:ARG534	5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			P:POS1	
10	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	5,1295	Bond	Bond	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	C:ARG534	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - C:ARG534	5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			P:POS1	

Table S38. 1POI-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H2 - A:ASP70:OD1	2,1417	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H	H-Donor	A:ASP70:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 - A:TYR332:O	1	Bond	Bond			P:POS1:H	
2	A:TYR332:OH - P:POS1:H2	2,4022	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H	H-Donor	A:TYR332:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 - P:POS1:O6	9	Bond	Bond			P:POS1:H	
3	P:POS1:O6 - P:POS1:H3	2,7651	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H3 - A:ASN83:OD1	9	Bond	Bond			P:POS1:H	
4	A:ASN83:OD1 - A:TRP82	8	Bond	Bond	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	D1	H-Acceptor
	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	3,9026	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked			A:TRP82	
5	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	5,3058	Bond	Bond	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1 - A:TRP82	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked			A:TRP82	
6	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	4,6874	Bond	Bond	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - A:TRP82	8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			A:TRP82	
7	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	4,9546	Bond	Bond	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	P:POS1 - A:TRP82	9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl			A:TRP82	

Table S39. 2ONC-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemist
1	P:POS1:H1 - A:TRP464:C P:POS1:H1 -	2,44701	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:TRP464:O	H-Acceptor
2	A:THR468:OG1	2,13658	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:THR468:OG1	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H2 - A:TYR597:C	1,85146	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:TYR597:O	H-Acceptor
4	A:TYR465:HA - P:POS1:C A:HIS600:HE1 -	2,91477	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR465:HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:O2	2,36344	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS600:HE1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
6	B:PHE461 - P:POS1	5,57838	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	B:HIS600 - P:POS1	4,37952	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	P:POS1:C14 - B:PRO247	4,8319	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:PRO247	Alkyl
9	P:POS1:C14 - B:CYS474	4,61388	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:CYS474	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C16 - B:PRO475	4,48613	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
11	A:PHE461 - P:POS1	4,90408	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
12	A:PHE461 - P:POS1:C21	4,97022	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl
13	A:TYR465 - P:POS1:C22	5,298	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
14	B:PHE461 - P:POS1	5,24448	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
15	B:PHE461 - P:POS1:C22	3,80685	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
16	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C16	4,72879	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
17	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C16	4,87213	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
18	B:TYR465 - P:POS1:C21	5,37323	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl
19	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C14	4,56747	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
20	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C16	5,24893	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl

Table S40. 2Z5X-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:ARG51:HH12 - P:POS1:O4	2,90673	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG51:HH12	H-Donor	P:POS1:O4	H-Acceptor
2	A:CYS406:HG - P:POS1:O5	1,78587	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:CYS406:HG	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLY66:O	2,37144	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLY66:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H3 - A:GLY443:O	1,84698	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	A:GLY443:O	H-Acceptor
5	A:GLY66:HA1 - P:POS1:O5	2,47799	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY66:HA1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
6	A:GLY67:HA2 - P:POS1:O6	1,74347	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:GLY67:HA2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
7	A:CYS406:SG - P:POS1 A:ARG51:C,O;THR52:N - P:POS1	5,09046	Other	Pi-Sulfur	A:CYS406:SG	Sulfur	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:GLY66:C,O;GLY67:N - P:POS1	4,79132	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:ARG51:C,O;THR52:N A:GLY66:C,O;GLY67:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
9	A:TYR444:C,O;MET445:N - P:POS1	3,97444	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:TYR444:C,O;MET445:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
10	A:ALA68 - P:POS1	4,03357	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	ET445:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
11	A:ALA68 - P:POS1	4,90172	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA68	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
12	A:ALA448 - P:POS1:C14	4,44137	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	A:ALA448	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
13	P:POS1:C14 - A:ILE23	4,16243	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	A:ILE23	Alkyl
14	P:POS1:C14 - A:MET445	5,00807	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	A:MET445	Alkyl
15	P:POS1:C16 - A:ARG51	4,47516	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl	A:ARG51	Alkyl
16	A:TYR69 - P:POS1	5,06098	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR69	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
17	A:TYR407 - P:POS1:C22	4,20902	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR407	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
18	A:TYR444 - P:POS1:C21	4,40208	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR444	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl
19	A:TYR444 - P:POS1:C22	4,90586	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR444	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
20	P:POS1 - A:ARG51	4,76511	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:ARG51	Alkyl
21	P:POS1 - A:MET445	4,83543	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:MET445	Alkyl

Table S41. 3LN1-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:GLN256:HE22 - P:POS1:O6 P:POS1:H1 - C:THR547:O	1,38764	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN256:HE22	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H2 - B:ASP254:O	2,24205	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	C:THR547:O	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H2 - B:ASP254:O	2,10166	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:ASP254:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H2 - B:ASP254:OD1	3,04326	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	B:ASP254:OD	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H3 - C:ASP333:OD1	1,64166	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	C:ASP333:OD	H-Acceptor
6	P:POS1 - B:LYS253	4,10448	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:LYS253	Alkyl

Table S42. 3V99-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:ARG438:HH22 - P:POS1:O5	2,74889	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG438:HH22	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H1 - A:GLN437:O	1,73444	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLN437:O	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H2 - P:POS1:O6	1,5345	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H3 - B:ARG438:O	2,15122	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H3	H-Donor	B:ARG438:O	H-Acceptor
5	A:ARG520:HD2 - P:POS1:O2	1,83564	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:ARG520:HD2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
6	B:ARG438:NH1 - P:POS1	3,47037	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:ARG438:NH1	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	A:MET440:C,O;LYS441:N - P:POS1	4,86586	Hydrophobic	Amide-Pi Stacked	A:MET440:C,O;LYS441:N	Amide	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	B:ARG438 - P:POS1	4,164	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ARG438	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
9	P:POS1:C14 - B:LEU288	3,63573	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:LEU288	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C16 - B:LEU288	4,75969	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl	B:LEU288	Alkyl
11	P:POS1:C16 - B:ARG438	4,04101	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl	B:ARG438	Alkyl
12	P:POS1:C21 - B:ARG438	3,75555	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	B:ARG438	Alkyl
13	P:POS1:C21 - B:LYS441	3,71533	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl	B:LYS441	Alkyl
14	P:POS1:C22 - A:ARG438	4,49942	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl	A:ARG438	Alkyl
15	P:POS1:C22 - A:LYS441	3,96084	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl	A:LYS441	Alkyl
16	P:POS1 - B:ARG438	4,6678	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl
17	P:POS1 - A:LYS441	5,35171	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:LYS441	Alkyl

Table S43. 5M6B-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:GLN304:N - P:POS1:O5	2,5999	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:GLN304:N	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H1 -	1,5249		Conventional				
2	B:LEU296:O	4	Hydrogen Bond	Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	B:LEU296:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 -	2,4826		Conventional				
3	A:THR303:OG1	8	Hydrogen Bond	Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:THR303:O G1	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H2 -	2,4784		Conventional				
4	A:GLN304:O	1	Hydrogen Bond	Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:GLN304:O	H-Acceptor
	B:PRO298:CD -	3,4277		Carbon Hydrogen				
5	P:POS1:O1	1	Hydrogen Bond	Bond	B:PRO298:CD	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
	B:ARG367:NH1 -	4,4570						
6	P:POS1	6	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	B:ARG367:NH1	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
		4,5921						
7	A:PHE239 - P:POS1	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:PHE239	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
		3,3707						
8	B:ALA228 - P:POS1:C16	3	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:ALA228	Alkyl	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
	A:PHE239 -	5,2005						
9	P:POS1:C14	8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE239	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
	A:PHE239 -	5,1482						
10	P:POS1:C16	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE239	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
	B:TYR297 -	5,3662						
11	P:POS1:C16	1	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR297	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
	B:PHE537 -	4,7087						
12	P:POS1:C14	7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE537	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
	B:PHE537 -	5,3588						
13	P:POS1:C16	5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE537	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
		5,0570						
14	B:PHE537 - P:POS1	1	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE537	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	B:PHE537 -	4,1014						
15	P:POS1:C21	9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE537	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl

Table S44. 6H5W-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:ASP358:HN - P:POS1:O5	2,54451	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:ASP358:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
2	A:TYR360:HH - P:POS1:O2	2,45434		Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
3	A:TYR360:HH - P:POS1:O6	2,42447	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR360:HH	H-Donor	P:POS1:O6	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H1 - A:ALA356:C	1,8919		Conventional Hydrogen Bond				
5	P:POS1:H2 - A:ASP358:C	2,16762	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:ASP358:O	H-Acceptor
6	A:TRP357:HA - P:POS1:O5	2,65976		Carbon Hydrogen Bond				
7	A:ASP358:HN - P:POS1	3,22899	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	A:ASP358:HN	H-Donor	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	A:ALA356 - P:POS1	4,88612		Alkyl				
9	A:HIS387 - P:POS1	4,82267	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS387	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
10	A:HIS387 - P:POS1:C21	3,92041						
11	A:HIS410 - P:POS1:C16	4,27326	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS410	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
12	A:HIS410 - P:POS1:C21	3,47489						

Table S45. 6H5X-Plicatipyron interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H1 - A:TRP464:O	2,2916 8	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:TRP464:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H1 - A:THR468:OG1	2,3514 2	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:THR468:OG1	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H2 - A:TYR597:O	1,6972	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H2	H-Donor	A:TYR597:O	H-Acceptor
4	A:TYR465:HA - P:POS1:O1	2,9376 4	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR465:HA	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
5	A:HIS600:HE1 - P:POS1:O2	2,5386 5	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:HIS600:HE1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
6	B:HIS600:HE1 - P:POS1:O3	2,0315 1	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:HIS600:HE1	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
7	B:PHE461 - P:POS1	5,5379 8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	B:HIS600 - P:POS1	4,2843 3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
9	P:POS1:C14 - B:CYS474	4,3582 2	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl	B:CYS474	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C16 - B:PRO475	4,3501 7	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
11	A:PHE461 - P:POS1	4,7731 1	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
12	A:PHE461 - P:POS1:C21	4,9684 5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl
13	A:TYR465 - P:POS1:C22	5,0170 8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
14	B:PHE461 - P:POS1	5,3309 2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
15	B:PHE461 - P:POS1:C22	3,7418 5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
16	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C16	4,6723 7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
17	B:TRP464 - P:POS1:C16	4,8323 3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl
18	B:TYR465 - P:POS1:C21	5,2298 7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C21	Alkyl
19	B:TYR465 - P:POS1:C22	5,3845 1	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TYR465	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C22	Alkyl
20	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C14	4,0011 3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C14	Alkyl
21	B:HIS600 - P:POS1:C16	5,1310 4	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C16	Alkyl

Table S46. 1C2O-galantamine interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	C:ARG534:CD - P:POS1:O1	3,3041 6	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	C:ARG534:C D	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H7 - B:GLU376:OE2	3,0955 3	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H7	H-Donor	B:GLU376:O E2	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H15 - B:GLU376:OE2	2,9194 4	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H15	H-Donor	B:GLU376:O E2	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H19 - C:ALA530:O	2,2367 8	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H19	H-Donor	C:ALA530:O	H-Acceptor
5	B:GLU376:OE2 - P:POS1	4,9541 3	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	B:GLU376:O E2	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
6	B:TRP385 - P:POS1	5,1963 7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:TRP385	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	B:VAL379 - P:POS1	4,3144 2	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:VAL379	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
8	C:ALA530 - P:POS1:C17	4,0512 4	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	C:ALA530	Alkyl	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
9	P:POS1:C17 - B:LEU380	3,7928	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl	B:LEU380	Alkyl
10	P:POS1:C17 - C:ARG534	3,8036 5,1104	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl	C:ARG534	Alkyl
11	B:TRP385 - P:POS1:C17	3 4,9826	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP385	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
12	B:TRP385 - P:POS1	1 4,3941	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP385	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
13	B:TRP385 - P:POS1:C17	6 4,8216	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP385	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
14	P:POS1 - B:VAL379	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:VAL379	Alkyl
15	P:POS1 - B:LEU380	5,303	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:LEU380	Alkyl

Table S47. 1POI-galantamine interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR128:OH -	2,9415	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR128:OH	H-Donor	P:POS1:O1	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O1	4	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR128:OH			
2	A:TYR128:OH -	2,5990	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR128:OH	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:O3	6	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1			
3	A:GLU197:OE2	2,3638	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU197:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H1 -	2,8953	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1			
4	A:GLU197:OE1	1	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU197:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H9 -	2,7138	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H9			
5	A:GLU197:OE2	5	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:GLU197:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H19 -	2,5129	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	A:TRP82:C			
6	A:THR122:O	8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	9	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	A:TRP82:CB - P:POS1	3,9771	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C1			
7	A:TRP82:CB - P:POS1	3,7735	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	7	Alkyl	A:LEU125	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C17 - A:LEU125	2	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82			
8	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	4,4320	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82			
9	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	3,8582	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP82	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	A:TRP82 - P:POS1	6	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR114			
10	A:TYR114 - P:POS1:C17	4,9525	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR114	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
	A:TYR114 - P:POS1:C17	8	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR128			
11	A:TYR128 - P:POS1:C17	4,7769	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR128	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C17	Alkyl
	A:TYR128 - P:POS1:C17	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR128			
12	A:TYR128 - P:POS1:C17	5,3206	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR128	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	A:TYR128 - P:POS1:C17	3	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS438			
13	A:HIS438 - P:POS1	4	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS438	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	A:HIS438 - P:POS1	4	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS438			

Table S48. 2ONC-sitagliptin interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR597:HH -	2,40701	Hydrogen Bond;Halogen	Conventional Hydrogen Bond;Halogen (Fluorine)	A:TYR597:HH	H-Donor;Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F1	H-Acceptor; Halogen
	P:POS1:H13 -							
2	A:PHE461:O	1,57874	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H13	H-Donor	A:PHE461:O	H-Acceptor
	B:TYR465:HA -	2,88886	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:TYR465:HA			
3	P:POS1:N3	2,88886	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:PRO475:HD	H-Donor	P:POS1:N3	H-Acceptor
	B:PRO475:HD1 -	2,94273	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	1			
4	- P:POS1:F2	2,94273	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:PRO475:HD	H-Donor	P:POS1:F2	H-Acceptor
	B:PRO475:HD2 -	2,9797	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	2			
5	- P:POS1:F2	2,9797	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:PRO475:HD	H-Donor	P:POS1:F2	H-Acceptor
	B:HIS600:HE1 -	2,50305	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:HIS600:HE1			
6	P:POS1:F6	2,50305	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:HIS600:HE1	H-Donor	P:POS1:F6	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H1 -	3,01055	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1			
7	A:TYR597:O	3,01055	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H1	H-Donor	A:TYR597:O	H-Acceptor
	P:POS1:H4 -	2,26045	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H4			
8	P:POS1:F3	2,26045	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H4	H-Donor Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F3	H-Acceptor
	A:GLN598:CD -	2,85987	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	A:GLN598:CD			
9	P:POS1:F3	2,85987	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	A:GLN598:OE	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F3	Halogen
	A:GLN598:OE1 -	3,38999	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	1			
10	- P:POS1:F1	3,38999	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	A:GLN598:OE	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F1	Halogen
	B:TYR597:O -	3,29708	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:TYR597:O			
11	P:POS1:F5	3,29708	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:TYR597:O	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F5	Halogen
	B:GLN598:O -	3,39494	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:GLN598:O			
12	P:POS1:F6	3,39494	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:GLN598:O	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F6	Halogen
	B:HIS600:NE2 -	3,30113	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:HIS600:NE2			
13	P:POS1:F2	3,30113	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:HIS600:NE2	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F2	Halogen
	B:HIS600:NE2 -	3,37549	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:HIS600:NE2			
14	P:POS1:F3	3,37549	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	B:HIS600:NE2	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F3	Halogen
	P:POS1:O1 -	3,44171	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	P:POS1:O1			
15	P:POS1:F4	3,44171	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	P:POS1:O1	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F4	Halogen
	P:POS1:N2 -	3,41504	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	P:POS1:N2			
16	P:POS1:F5	3,41504	Halogen	Halogen (Fluorine)	P:POS1:N2	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:F5	Halogen
	P:POS1:H12 -	2,67979	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H12			
17	A:PHE461	2,67979	Hydrogen Bond	Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H12	H-Donor	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1 -	4,8203	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	P:POS1			
18	P:POS1	4,8203	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	B:TYR597 -	5,08749	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:TYR597			
19	P:POS1	5,08749	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	B:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1 -	5,42037	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	P:POS1			
20	A:TYR597	5,42037	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals
	P:POS1:C11 -	4,7764	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C11			
21	B:PRO475	4,7764	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:C11	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl
	A:TYR597 -	5,34065	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597			
22	P:POS1	5,34065	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
	A:TYR597 -	5,16809	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597			
23	P:POS1:C11	5,16809	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C11	Alkyl
	P:POS1:C11	5,16809	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR597			

24	B:PHE461 - P:POS1 B:TRP464 -	4,96275	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1 P:POS1:C1	Alkyl
25	P:POS1:C11 B:HIS600 -	4,94922	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	1 P:POS1:C1	Alkyl
26	P:POS1:C11	4,98264	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	1	Alkyl

Table S49. 2Z5X-clorgiline interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H10 - A:ASN125:OD1	2,2122 2	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H10	H-Donor Halogen Acceptor	A:ASN125:OD1	H-Acceptor
2	A:GLU492:C - P:POS1:CI1	3,2742 3,5894	Halogen	Halogen (Cl, Br, I)	A:GLU492:C	Halogen Acceptor	P:POS1:CI1	Halogen
3	A:HIS488 - P:POS1	3 4,4249	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi Stacked	A:HIS488	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
4	P:POS1:CI1 - A:ARG129	8 3,5878	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:CI1	Alkyl	A:ARG129	Alkyl
5	P:POS1:CI1 - A:ARG493	8 4,8130	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	P:POS1:CI1	Alkyl	A:ARG493	Alkyl
6	A:TYR124 - P:POS1:C13	9 4,9292	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR124	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C13	Alkyl
7	A:TRP128 - P:POS1	5 4,2001	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TRP128	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
8	A:HIS488 - P:POS1:CI1	3 5,0214	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS488	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:CI1	Alkyl
9	A:HIS488 - P:POS1	9 3,7800	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS488	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
10	P:POS1 - A:ARG129	9	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:ARG129	Alkyl

Table S50. 3LN1-tiaprofenic acid interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	C:ARG297:HH12 - P:POS1:O3	1,8557	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:ARG297:HH1 2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O 3	H-Acceptor
2	C:ARG297:HH21 - P:POS1:S1	2,43413	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:ARG297:HH2 1	H-Donor	P:POS1:S1 P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
3	C:ARG297:HH21 - P:POS1:O3	2,01161	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:ARG297:HH2 1	H-Donor	3 P:POS1:O	H-Acceptor
4	C:ASN556:HD21 - P:POS1:O3	2,87806	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	C:ASN556:HD21	H-Donor	3 C:ILE544: O	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H12 - C:ILE544:O	2,0323	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H12	H-Donor	O	H-Acceptor
6	C:LYS543:NZ - P:POS1	4,6588	Electrostatic	Pi-Cation	C:LYS543:NZ	Positive	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	C:VAL540:HG12 - P:POS1	2,53411	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	C:VAL540:HG12	C-H Pi- Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
8	P:POS1 - C:LYS543	4,97705	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Orbitals	C:LYS543	Alkyl
9	P:POS1 - C:ILE544	4,0885	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Orbitals	C:ILE544	Alkyl
10	P:POS1 - C:LYS543	4,07665	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Orbitals	C:LYS543	Alkyl

Table S51. 3V99-Acetaminophen interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
P:POS1:H9 - B:GLN437:O	1,89432	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H9	H-Donor	B:GLN437:O	H-Acceptor
B:ARG438:HD2 - P:POS1:O2	2,63851	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:ARG438:HD2	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
P:POS1 - A:ARG438	4,05762	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:ARG438	Alkyl
P:POS1 - B:ARG438	4,23434	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	B:ARG438	Alkyl

Table S52. 5M6B-kojic acid interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	B:TRP230:N - P:POS1:O4	3,09789	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:TRP230:N	H-Donor	P:POS1:O4	H-Acceptor
2	B:TRP301:N - P:POS1:O3	3,09987	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:TRP301:N	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H5 - B:ALA228:O	2,34341	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H5	H-Donor	B:ALA228:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H6 - A:GLY299:O	1,77157	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H6	H-Donor	A:GLY299:O	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H4 - B:GLY299:O	2,70795	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H4	H-Donor	B:GLY299:O	H-Acceptor
6	A:VAL300:CG1 - P:POS1	3,75915	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	A:VAL300:CG1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	B:VAL300:CG1 - P:POS1	3,52284	Hydrophobic	Pi-Sigma	B:VAL300:CG1	C-H	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals

Table S53. 6H5W-atenonol interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	P:POS1:H14 - A:ALA354:O	2,1478	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H14	H-Donor	A:ALA354:O	H-Acceptor
2	P:POS1:H14 - A:GLU384:OE2	2,9632	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H14	H-Donor	A:GLU384:OE2	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H21 - A:ALA356:O	2,1245	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H21	H-Donor	A:ALA356:O	H-Acceptor
4	P:POS1:H7 - A:HIS383:NE2	2,4391	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H7	H-Donor	A:HIS383:NE2	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H7 - A:GLU384:OE2	2,8499	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H7	H-Donor	A:GLU384:OE2	H-Acceptor
6	A:GLU411:OE2 - P:POS1	4,2196	Electrostatic	Pi-Anion	A:GLU411:OE2	Negative	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	A:HIS383 - P:POS1:C6	4,1537	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:HIS383	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C6	Alkyl
8	A:PHE457 - P:POS1:C5	4,541	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE457	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C5	Alkyl
9	A:TYR520 - P:POS1:C5	5,3210	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR520	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C5	Alkyl
10	A:TYR523 - P:POS1:C5	7	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C5	Alkyl
11	A:TYR523 - P:POS1:C5	3,6860	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C5	Alkyl
12	A:TYR523 - P:POS1:C6	4,3806	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C6	Alkyl
13	A:TYR523 - P:POS1:C6	5	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:TYR523	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1:C6	Alkyl

Table S54. 6H5X-lisinopril interaction categories, species and molecular docking distance

No	Name	Distance	Category	Types	From	From Chemistry	To	To Chemistry
1	A:TYR597:HH - P:POS1:O3	2,75226	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	A:TYR597:H	H-Donor	P:POS1:O3	H-Acceptor
2	B:GLN598:HE21 - P:POS1:O5	2,43506	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	B:GLN598:H E21	H-Donor	P:POS1:O5	H-Acceptor
3	P:POS1:H28 - A:GLN598:O	2,16595	Hydrogen Bond	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H28	H-Donor	A:GLN598 :O	H-Acceptor
4	B:HIS600:HE1 - P:POS1:N2	2,60159	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	B:HIS600:HE 1	H-Donor	P:POS1:N2	H-Acceptor
5	P:POS1:H22 - P:POS1:O2	2,54797	Hydrogen Bond	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	P:POS1:H22	H-Donor	P:POS1:O2	H-Acceptor
6	A:HIS600 - P:POS1	4,36709	Hydrophobic	Pi-Pi T-shaped	A:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals
7	B:PRO475 - P:POS1	4,49227	Hydrophobic	Alkyl	B:PRO475	Alkyl	P:POS1	Alkyl
8	A:PHE461 - P:POS1	5,38498	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	A:PHE461	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
9	B:TRP464 - P:POS1	5,36782	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:TRP464	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
10	B:HIS600 - P:POS1	4,43896	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	B:HIS600	Pi-Orbitals	P:POS1	Alkyl
11	P:POS1 - A:CYS474	5,17171	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:CYS474	Alkyl
12	P:POS1 - A:PRO475	4,96114	Hydrophobic	Pi-Alkyl	P:POS1	Pi-Orbitals	A:PRO475	Alkyl

Table S55. Toxicity parametres of the compounds

Compounds	Italipyron	Helipyron	Bisnorhelipyron	Norhelipyron	Plicatipyron
Toxicity Parametres					
Hepatotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Neurotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Nephrotoxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Respiratory toxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Cardiotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Carcinogenicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Immunotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Mutagenicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Cytotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Ecotoxicity	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive
Clinical toxicity	Active	Active	Active	Active	Active
Nutritional toxicity	Active	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Active
Predicted LD₅₀ (mg/kg)	1600	1000	1000	1000	1600
Predicted Toxicity Class	4	4	4	4	4